

LEGAL AND PEDAGOGICAL BASES OF PREPARATION OF CHILDREN FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SOCIAL PROTECTION

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Annotation. This article is dedicated to the protection of children's rights and freedoms. About the guarantee of the rights and freedoms of the child, regardless of his origin, lineage, race, religion, language, nationality. It is in this context that reforms, measures, insights and advice are provided to improve the legal literacy of the next generation. A number of recommendations have been made to educate the younger generation in a free and democratic, humane spirit.

Keywords: democratic, law freedom, obligation, humanity, patriotism, constitution, convention.

INTRODUCTION

Educating the younger generation in the spirit of freedom, democracy and humanity, raising them in the spirit of the full human being and protecting and ensuring their rights and freedoms is very important for any society that aims to build a democratic, legal state based on civil society. important and topical. Like all democracies, this issue, which is the education of the younger generation and the formation of a legal culture in the field of children's rights, is an important and topical issue for Uzbekistan.

From the first days of independence, the country has focused on the issues of youth, their upbringing as citizens with their own civic position, ensuring their rights, freedoms and legitimate interests as a priority of state policy. This is evidenced by the fact that at the time of our declaration of independence, on November 20, 1991, a special law "On the Fundamentals of State Youth Policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted. This Law defines the purpose of youth policy, the powers of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of state youth policy, the content and essence of the laws on state youth policy, the principle of priority of the norms of international agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan in this regard. mentioned. This means that the issue of youth policy is reflected in the Constitution of independent Uzbekistan in 1992, this year Uzbekistan acceded to the Convention on the Rights of the Child, one of the main documents of the United Nations, and on the basis of these documents. During this period, more than 100 laws related to children and youth were adopted, and in 2008 the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child" was adopted, which is a special law in this area. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child", which came into force in January, is aimed at regulating the relationship of children under 18 years of age to determine the legal status of children, legal guarantees of children's rights and freedoms.

It should be noted that more than half of the provisions of the law are devoted to the protection of children's rights. Based on the above, it can be said that over the past period, the country has created an international and national legal framework for the legal protection of children, and they are being implemented. These legal documents pay special attention to the formation and development of the legal culture of children, as well as all other segments of the population in the field of children's rights. Legal education is important in this regard. As a result of the implementation of relevant international documents, laws and resolutions of the parliament, the ideas of the President, relevant decrees and orders, today in our country preschool and general secondary education, higher education and higher education. A system of legal education has been created in postgraduate education. The study of children's rights has become an integral part of this system.

MAIN PART

The Convention on the Rights of the Child is the most comprehensive and forward-looking document that has the force of international law on the rights of the child. Adopted unanimously by the UN General Assembly on November 20, 1989. The Convention develops the provisions of the 1959 Declaration of the Rights of the Child. The Declaration declared that "Humanity is obliged to give children all the best it has." The Convention incorporates the laws on the rights of the child into this Declaration and other international instruments. The Convention on the Rights of the Child is of equal importance to peoples in all parts of the world, with the primary goal of protecting the interests of children as much as possible. It consists of an introduction, 3 parts, and 54 articles. Under the Convention, any person under the age of 18 is considered a child unless national law sets a minimum age for puberty. The Convention on the Rights of the Child is a set of civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights. It requires that children, among other things, be provided with minimum standards of health and environmental safety, access to health care and food, clothing, and shelter, in order for them to freely develop their moral, mental, and spiritual abilities. According to the Convention, a child has the right to take an active part in his or her development, to express his or her views, and to be taken into account in resolving issues affecting his or her life.

The Convention contains provisions on the right of the child to life and healthy development, the right to adoption, the rights of orphans and refugee children, as well as the rights of delinquent children, and the primary role of the family and parents in the care and protection of children. , recognizes its commitment to helping children. Non-discrimination against children is an important principle of the Convention.

Children should be able to exercise their rights without discrimination, regardless of race, body color, sex, language, religion, political or other beliefs, national, ethnic or social origin, property status, state of health, parent or legal guardian or any other circumstances. The Convention on the Rights of the Child entered into force on 2 September 1990. The Republic of Uzbekistan joined it on December 9, 1992. States that have ratified or acceded to the Convention regularly submit national reports to the Committee on the Rights of the Child on measures to

implement it. The first national report on the implementation of this Convention in the Republic of Uzbekistan was prepared in 1997. The articles of the Convention regulate the child's right to life, well-being, education, name, citizenship, individuality, communication with parents living separately, and freedom of expression.

The Convention prohibits ill-treatment, exploitation and discrimination against children. The state and parents have a responsibility to ensure the rights and freedoms of children. Under the Convention, all treatment of children must be based on the principle of the best interests of the child. This criterion also applies to the attitude of parents towards their children. This convention is also known as the Universal Constitution of the Rights of the Child. It is the first legally binding international treaty on the rights of the child in human history. Its provisions are not declarative. In 1992, the Republic of Uzbekistan ratified the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child and undertook international obligations to comply with and implement its provisions. Despite the fact that more than a hundred laws regulate the rights and freedoms of the child in our country, on January 7, 2008 the law "On guarantees of the rights of the child" came into force. In connection with this date, on July 17 this year, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution "On approval of the Program of events dedicated to the 30th anniversary of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child."

Within the framework of this program, events are held to explain the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the rights and obligations of state and non-governmental organizations dealing with children's rights, methods and forms of protection of children's rights in case of violation. The provisions of the Convention on the Rights of the Child, international standards are promoted among the population, and information is provided on the relevant state and public structures working in the interests of children on the ground. It is important to publish not only the text of the convention, but also special literature, posters and materials in Uzbek, Karakalpak and Russian, which will help to raise the level of education in the social and cultural development of the child. A meeting of the Interagency Coordinating Council on the implementation of the Convention on the Rights of the Child in Uzbekistan was held in Tashkent. Representatives of governmental and non-governmental organizations, as well as experts from international organizations discussed priority issues in this area. This year also marks the 30th anniversary of the adoption of the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC). The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child is a UN treaty ratified by most countries in the world and plays an important role in improving the lives of children around the world. A number of measures have been taken in our country to ensure the rights of the child.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a resolution on additional measures to further strengthen the guarantees of the rights of the child. The participants noted the political will and consistency of the Uzbek government in implementing the recommendations of the UN Committee on the Rights of the Child. At the same time, they stressed the need to further strengthen the monitoring of children's rights and the mechanisms for dealing with complaints

filed by children themselves and on their behalf. Among other issues, council members discussed the process of developing a five-year action plan to meet the needs of children deprived of parental care. "It is gratifying that the government is developing plans to create a family-like alternative environment for children left without parental care. To strengthen the family support system, an action plan should be developed for the deinstitutionalization of children deprived of parental care and the creation of alternative family-like conditions for them.

To do this, we need to focus on local community initiatives to change the practice of placing children in large institutions and prevent them from being separated from their families," said Sasha Graumann, UNICEF Representative in Uzbekistan. Another important recommendation for meeting the needs of socially vulnerable children is to expand the scope of funding for social protection of children. Supporting low-income families is important as economic reforms continue. The participants of the meeting stressed that the social protection of children should be a priority.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Guarantees of the rights and interests of the child Our people have always paid special attention to the younger generation as the successors of our lives. It can be seen that the upbringing of the younger generation is also based on the views of our great scholars Abu Nasr Farobi, Ibn Sino, Kaykovus, Sahibkiran Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi. At the same time, our sacred hadiths focus on family relations, the duties of parents and children, the impact of upbringing on the child's mind, parental responsibility. Our great ancestor Abu Ali Ibn Sina emphasized the importance of observing a child's behavior and inculcating good habits in him, and the need to introduce him to the basics of literacy, vocational training and the arts in a timely manner. According to the scholar, a father should give his child a good name, take care of him when he is older, protect him from bad influences, and teach him to solve problems that are not complicated when he is six years old. Indeed, educating the younger generation will never lose its relevance. This noble tradition has become more widespread during the years of independence and has become one of the priorities of our state policy. As a result, a large-scale work is being carried out in our country today to ensure the rights and interests of children, to care for their life and health, to prevent discrimination, to protect their honor and dignity, to ensure equal rights and opportunities.

To help every child to develop physically, intellectually and spiritually, to bring them up in the spirit of patriotism, tolerance and peace, to acquaint them with our national traditions and values, achievements of world culture, to develop scientific and artistic creativity, to strengthen cooperation between government and non-governmental organizations. The reduction in crime and delinquency between the two countries is also a testament to the scale of the work in this area. Improving the legal framework of the industry is important for their successful implementation. Therefore, over the past years, measures have been taken to create a national legal framework that guarantees the rights of the child at the level of international standards, along with creating

conditions for young people to get a perfect education and develop their talents. First of all, it should be noted that the Constitution fully guarantees the rights of the child.

On this basis, five international conventions have been ratified and more than a dozen laws have been adopted. In particular, the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child and the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child" fully guarantee the rights and interests of children. In accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On guardianship and trusteeship", comprehensive care is provided to persons in need of guardianship and trusteeship, in particular, children deprived of parental care. At the same time, the prevention of juvenile delinquency and delinquency is being consistently ensured, and the protection of their rights and legitimate interests in courts and other institutions is being ensured. Uzbekistan has also acceded to the Convention on the Minimum Age for Recruitment (Geneva, 26 June 1973) and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Child Labor (Geneva, 17 June 1999). is doing. It should be noted that foreign experts positively assess the care provided to children in our country.

Judge Renate Winter, an international expert on children's rights, said: "Uzbekistan is fully implementing the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child and has a strong legal framework in place. It is noteworthy that the country pays special attention to improving the legislation in this area and international cooperation," he said. The Law on Guarantees of the Rights of the Child for the first time clarifies the meaning of such concepts as children, orphans, children in need of social protection, and children with disabilities. It strengthens the powers of state bodies and public associations to ensure the rights of the child and create the necessary conditions for their implementation. The adoption of a number of Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child" and "On Prevention of Juvenile Delinquency and Juvenile Delinquency", which incorporate international and national documents on the rights of the child, further strengthened the legal framework for protecting the rights and interests of children. It should be noted that in the world ranking compiled by the international organization "Save the Children", Uzbekistan is included in the top ten countries that take great care of children's health. Every effort is being made to further improve the rights and interests of children, their socio-economic, cultural and educational conditions, to make them a decisive force in our future as a comprehensively developed generation. This will strengthen our confidence in the future.

CONCLUSION

In short, the country has created and is improving the legal framework and institutional framework for the development of a legal culture of children's rights. However, the operation of laws, the effectiveness of their mechanisms depends, first of all, on the level of legal culture of the population. And it can't be achieved without education. Therefore, in addition to the development of human rights education in the country, special education on the rights of children, who make up a large part of its population, is becoming a topical issue today. In this regard, a number of reforms are being carried out to raise the legal awareness of children and increase the legal awareness of the population about the rights of the child. The Constitution of the Republic of

Uzbekistan enshrines the following principles of the legal status of a person and a citizen, which are the basis for the exercise of their rights and obligations, ie a set of guiding ideas:

- 1) the supremacy of international law in the field of human and civil rights and freedoms;
- 2) inseparability of fundamental rights and freedoms;
- 3) direct exercise of rights and freedoms;
- 4) inadmissible restriction of rights and freedoms;
- 5) the state guarantees the rights and freedoms of individuals and citizens;
- 6) equality;
- 7) that the exercise of one's rights and freedoms must not infringe on the rights and freedoms of others.

The human rights enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan establish the scope of individual freedom and self-determination, its autonomy, and regulate social relations and relations on the basis of universally recognized international norms and standards in the field of human rights and freedoms. and coordinates, the state prevents the unreasonable interference of man in the sphere of personal freedom, sets the boundaries of its activities by preventing the absolute domination and arbitrariness of state structures, the criteria of the relationship between man and the state, the state for its activities and defines his responsibility to the person. The constitutional basis of any democratic state is human rights and freedoms. In this sense, it is no coincidence that the section "Fundamental rights, freedoms and duties of man and citizen" has a special place in the Constitution of our country. Also, as noted above, the section "Basic Principles" of the Constitution reinforces the basic ideas that emphasize the supreme value of man, his life, liberty, honor, dignity and other inalienable rights. they also apply to children who are full-fledged members of society, as well as those who have additional rights and privileges as a certain vulnerable group.

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